

Publication of Version 3.0 of the DDI specification in April was a signal event for the DDI Alliance. A flurry of activity followed, particularly in May and June. This issue of DDI Directions reports on some of that activity and looks ahead to plans for Fall.

Mary Vardigan, Director, DDI Alliance

Alliance Expert Committee Meeting

The Expert Committee met at Stanford University in May in conjunction with the annual meeting of the International Association of Social Science Information Service and Technology (IASSIST). On the agenda were topics including:

- Building Alliance membership
- Publicizing DDI
- Mapping to other metadata standards, with an emphasis on METS
- DDI tools
- Transitioning from DDI 2 to 3.0
- DDI training

Recent DDI Presentations

The IASSIST program featured several DDI-related presentations and two pre-conference workshops.

Joachim Wackerow presented a poster on DDI at the fourth Conference of German Council for Social and Economic Data (RatSWD) in Wiesbaden, Germany, June 19–20. The RatSWD plays a central role in the German

Expert Committee meeting, May 31, 2008

From left, Dan Smith and Jeremy Iverson, Algenta Technologies; Tom Piazza (past DDI Alliance Chair), University of California, Berkeley; Hans Jorgen Marker (current Chair), Danish Data Archive

data landscape, advising on the development of the German data infrastructure.

On June 18, the day before the conference, the **German Institute for the Study of Labor (IZA)** organized a workshop at the same venue on “**Comparability of DDI/SDMX.**” Arofan Gregory and Pascal Heus made a three-faceted presentation (DDI, SDMX, and the relationships between them and to other metadata standards). About 20 people attended the workshop, which was designed to promote discussion of metadata standards in the research and service data centers.

survey methods related to design, data collection, quality assurance, analysis, and archiving.

Fall DDI Training

DDI 3.0 training, sponsored by German Social Science Infrastructure Services, Centre for Survey Research and Methodology (**GESIS-ZUMA**), will again be offered at **Schloss Dagstuhl, Leibniz Center for Informatics**, November 3–7, 2008. This **workshop** is geared toward the staff of archives and data producing agencies. The multi-day structure of the workshop provides participants

sponsored by the **DDI Alliance**, **GESIS**, **Minnesota Population Center**, and the **Open Data Foundation**. The premise of this workshop is that with the publication of DDI 3.0, there is now a question of how best to implement it and thus a need to document best practices to support interoperability and sharing of metadata. The focused expert workshop is designed to produce two papers addressing this need: one on technical best practices and the other dealing with organizational approaches, governance, and content. These will form the basis of ongoing work in this area within the DDI community. The intention is to publish these papers on the DDI Alliance Web site and in other locations as appropriate.

Joachim Wackerow and Wendy Thomas at the Conference of the German Council for Social and Economic Data on June 19

Wendy Thomas, Joachim Wackerow, and Mary Vardigan gave DDI-related papers at the International Conference on Survey Methods in Multinational, Multiregional, and Multicultural Contexts (**3MC**), held in Berlin, Germany, June 25–28. The 3MC conference presented state-of-the-art research on all aspects of cross-national and cross-cultural

with an opportunity for in-depth assistance on the specialized features of DDI that are important to their organizations’ activities.

Best Practices Workshop

The following week (November 10–14), there are plans for a Best Practice Workshop at Dagstuhl,

DDI Regional User Groups

Nikos Askitas from the Institute for the Study of Labor (IZA) in Bonn, Germany, and Joachim Wackerow (GESIS-ZUMA) are heading up plans for a regional European DDI Users Meeting, modeled on the successful Stata users meetings with the goal of providing a forum for information exchange among users and communication of specific needs back to the DDI Alliance. IZA has proposed to host the first such meeting in 2009 in Bonn, Germany, in September/October. North America could also host regional user meetings and ideally the geographic reach would extend over time.

New Alliance Member

We are pleased to announce that **Cornell University** has joined the Alliance. Bill Block, Director of the **Cornell Institute for Social and Economic Research (CISER)**, is the Alliance representative to the Expert Committee. ■